

Supplementary Material for “Agents on a LEASH: A Case Study in Micro-Managing Web Agent Behavior”

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Appendix A: Full Workflow for JAIR Pre-Submission Assessment

Task: Assess 4 JAIR Pre-Submission Criteria
Plan: Identify all new submissions

Step: Go to Login page
Pre-Sensing: None
Action: Go to <https://jair.org/index.php/jair/login>
Post-Sensing: Site should be <https://jair.org/index.php/jair/login> and login page is loaded

Step: Enter the Username
Pre-Sensing: Identify the input field named Username
Action: Enter the username <value> into the input field Username
Post-Sensing: The value in the input field Username should be <value>

Step: Enter the Password
Pre-Sensing: Identify the input field named Password
Action: Enter the password <value> into the input field Password
Post-Sensing: The value in the input field Password should be <value>

Step: Click the Login button
Pre-Sensing: Identify the button with "Login" on it
Action: Click the identified button
Post-Sensing: The login button should no longer be on the page

Step: Click on the All Active tab
Pre-Sensing: Identify the navigation tab called "All Active"
Action: Click on the identified navigation tab
Post-Sensing: The name of the clicked button should be "All Active"

Step: Get links to all of the active papers
Pre-Sensing: Find all of the buttons named "View" on this page with their associated paper ID
Action: Pull all "View" links into a list, with their associated paper ID
Post-Sensing: The list should have length > 0 if you find a "View" link

Step: Only keep the papers that are new
Pre-Sensing: The list of paper "View" links is not empty
Action: Compare this list to the list of papers we've processed in the past (from external storage)
Post-Sensing: The list of paper "View" links is not empty

Plan: Assess newly submitted papers, for each paper in the new submissions

Step: Click the Submissions button
Pre-Sensing: Identify the section link named "Submissions"
Action: Click on the link named "Submissions"
Post-Sensing: The button you clicked was named Submissions and you still observe a Submissions link in the navigation menu

Step: Click on the All Active tab
Pre-Sensing: Identify the navigation tab called "All Active"
Action: Click on the identified navigation tab

Post-Sensing: The name of the clicked button should be "All Active"
Step: Assess each paper for JAIR criteria
Pre-Sensing:
Action: Enter the password <value> into the input field Password
Post-Sensing: The value in the input field Password should be <value>
Step: Render Decision by Updating Spreadsheet
Pre-Sensing: Ensure decision output exists (JSON) for the paper
Action: Write the decision to external storage (spreadsheet)
Post-Sensing: The paper ID was written to external storage

Appendix B: Prompt given to the Comet browser

Log in to this page with the username [provided] and the password of [provided]

Click on the All Active tab. For each paper on this tab, find all of the View buttons associated with each paper ID, and create a list of each id and the link to the view button.

Next, for each paper on the list, follow the View button.

Now you are on the details page for that specific paper. On this page you will perform multiple tasks.

First, examine the PDF of the paper itself. This is a PDF file and it will either have a title called Article (PDF) or Article Text. If there is no PDF, output "No PDF" and the paper ID. If the paper does have a PDF, find all of the authors on the first page of the PDF and save them as a list.

Then, navigate to the Publication tab. On this tab, click on Contributors. You will see a list of authors for that paper. Compare the list of authors to the list of authors you pulled off of the PDF. If they are not the same, output "Mismatched authors" along with the paper ID and your reasoning as to why they are not the same.

Finally, click on the Workflow tab again. You will see a link toward the bottom called Comments for the Editor. If you do not see this link, output "No comments" and the paper ID.

If you do see this link, click on it to open a modal. In the modal there should be 3 separate answers to questions. If you do not see 3 separate answers, output "Not 3 answers" along with the paper ID and your reasoning why.

Finally, here is a link to a PDF in the correct format: <https://jair.org/index.php/jair/article/view/18965/27237>
If the submission does have a PDF article you can find, compare it to this reference PDF. The formats should be the same. If they are not, output "PDF Format error"

Do this for every single paper in the All Active tab. At the end of this, output a JSON with all of the results, per paper, with the paper id, any failure reasons (it's ok to have none), and the reasoning.